

New Caledonia Field Season 2018

06/08/18: Arrived in Noumea with Donna Whitney, Geoff Clarke,
Vasilis Chatzaras, Tim Chapman

Stayed at Auberge de Jeunesse de Noumea (X)

06/09/18: Shopping at Decathlon, Bricolage, Carrefour

Drive up west coast; large gas station

Lunch at gov. building

Questions:

→ What is the observable range of fluid-related features in the HP terrane of New Caledonia?

• How do these vary among different protoliths, and what does this reveal about fluid migration in subducting oceanic slabs?

→ How do the fluid features change w/increasing grade?

→

Other goals:

→ Is the mélange a mélange?

→ Observe other major outcrops of serpentinite

→ HP eclogite veins

→ Sample Poya basalts

- garnets w/ lawsonite + amphibole inclusions
- glaucophanites

To check:

• Poya basalt - composition of pyroxenes, etc. (only whole-rock data)

• Zerk et al metamorphic vs. metased. trend

• paragonite

• piemontite (Sivritsis)

• Claude Ouer, Casades, Shvedskia blueschist

Spandler et al, 2008 ^{table} → Fig. 2 20° 15' 44"
Newaka Stream 2 Mangovitch 164° 23' 23"

when get back:

• data from Chazel et al, 2001

• Pam-Ouegou map digital

06/10/18

Wake up: 6:00 AM, blue sky day

- Pam - Ouegoa map
 - blue metabasalt (OIB)
 - purple "basic rocks" (MORB; titanite, ~~also~~ epidote cores)
- MP seeps, along NE coast (see Fitzherbert & Clarke Fig. 2)

Stop 1: (8:30 AM) Zone 1

20° 22.9180'

164° 24.8360'

- layer-parallel foliation
- Spessartine-ferro-glauv. grade
- siltstone protolith (in the upper part of this package is the fm. a charbon)
- randomly oriented glaucophane, some siliceous layers, change in steepness of fabric

Stop 2: (9:00 AM) Zone 1

20° 22.1132'

164° 24.6678'

- garnet, glauc., ep
- NC18-01 - ep or lawsonite?
 - weathered blocky outcrop with
 - qtz. veins
 - fresher outcrop on S. side of road (white blocks look white instead of green)

Step 4 Zone 2A (outcrop near school)

→ near lawsonite ep. transition; work of Black

→ start to find abundant garnet

→ veins of clinzoisite (fluid-based leaching)

→ lawsonite found as inclusions in clinzoisite

→ 20° 20.3305' (turn off on dirt road by

164° 26.3489' yellow house with green roof)

NC18-02

• clinzoisite coarser-grained; probably not lawsonite here

• metabasaltic block near metasedimentary rocks

* watch for clinzoisite veins when cutting the billet

10:45 - Stopped @ Pacific store/gas station in Ovego
moving west/NW along Route de Pam (W of Rt. 7)

Step 5 Zone 1

20° 20.1389'

164° 25.1712'

metasedimentary Diabot outcrop

• fine-grained glauc. clear foliations + crenulations

Step 7 Zone 3

NC18-03

20° 19.2862'

164° 22.0207'

glaucophanite, more abundant clinzoisite veins

Some w/garnet grouped in them

• if you keep heading east up the ridge, there is

more outcrop

• near large shear zone

Stop 8

Zone 3

12:15 PM

20° 18.9604'

164° 21.0509'

• omph. in albite

• phengite [?] paragonite• albite forming during decompression [?], consuming omph.• ^{Dichot} metasediments, slightly graphitic

1:00 PM - Lunch at ruin

20° 14.5194'

164° 18.2702'

1:45 PM

Stop 9

Zone 3

Quarry at 20° 15.2291'

164° 18.3660'

• garnet-rich metabasite (upper-left black portion of Fitzherbert Fig. 2)

• qtz.-rich veins

• Barroisne paper - predicted UHP

NC18-04

• fresh eclogite from upper portion of quarry

• garnet size ↑ from bottom to top

• meta-tuff (?) siliceous layers mm - cm thick w/ glauc. + omph.-rich (separately) layers

Stop 10 3:15 PM Zone 4

garnet barrosite, omphacite; Povebo meta-basalt

20° 13.9115'

164° 19.1779'

NC18-05 A & B

A - large, main outcrop

B - large phengites

Stop 11 3:45 PM

20° 14.4175'

164° 20.4251'

NC18-06 - took 2 samples - need to pair down to one

→ finer-grained Povebo meta-basalt

→ fracture-network/veins - clinzoisite A

Stop 12

20° 15.8076'

164° 23.3889'

NC18-07A

→ Diabot metasediments

NC18-07B+C

→ green, sep. lenses

→ talc-rich

* → walk again w/ Mario

06/11/18 Day 2

Wake up: 6:00 AM, blue sky day w/ clouds train on the horizon

Today target - Balade mine, eclogite veins

Stop 1: Balade mine Zone 3?20° 19.6500'

164° 25.7399'

glaucophanites; garnet veining

Some Cu mineralization

NC18-08

glaucophanite in stream float; large mica

Unsure of where the glaucophanite comes from
metasediments in creek show consistent NW/SE strikePark at 20° 19.7056'

164° 25.5978'

Stop 2: Col de Amoss Zone 320° 18.2387'

164° 24.9476'

- some carbonaceous material here (suppression of grain size)
- metasediment; schists
- W flank? (dipping west)

Stop 3:20° 17.5896'

164° 25.0745'

albite, actinolite, epidote

NC18-09 A, B, C

A: gt. + qtz. - rich layers caught up in a shear zone

B: Serpentinite near ditch

C: biotite, epidote near serpentinite

Shear zones

Stop 4

→ eclogite block

· visibly zoned garnets

· phg. + garnet veins (elongate)

· green-colored ^{graph.} rxn. rims

NC18-10

eclogite vein outcrop A

Stop 5

20° 25.8135'

164° 38.9800'

talc, serpentinite

Stop 6

20° 22.1472'

164° 23.6502'

06/12/18 Day 3

Trying to do road drive S of river

Stop 1

20° 24.7516'

164° 24.3679'

- low-grade metasediments w/ consistent qtz veins (late stage)
- nicely developed oronulation cleavage
- Road is not driveable

Stop 2

20° 24.6954' (by telephone poles)

164° 24.2515'

- slightly more cohesive metasediments less small qtz veins,
- larger qtz vein in line with foliation
- is there garnet or some sulfide in these? tiny...

Stop 3

trying to find the serp. - metabasite lens

20° 22.9357'

164° 25.2660'

metasediments, fresh outcrop

Oronulation similar development as Stop 2

slightly bluer rocks? no sulfides visible in hand sample

Stop 4

20° 21.9218'

164° 24.1112'

NC18-11 A, B

→ epidote blueschist boulders off road near creek

Stop 5

20° 22.1992'

164° 23.6502'

→ blueschist near quarry

NC18-12Stop 6

20° 22.9376'

164° 22.7955'

→ creek w/ some rocks from quarry (likely)
other than that, no rocksStop 7

→ other side of Dishot (past the landfill)

20° 20.7160'

164° 25.1352'

• more of the siliceous blue rock they

Stop 8

20° 20' 50.47"

164° 24' 56.3"

cont'd down diff. road - dead end w/ metaseds

Stop 9 (quarry)

NC18-13

appearance of garnet in the siliceous
blue rock used for roads

20° 20.7230'

164° 25.1336'

Lunch

Stop 10

beginning of road transect

- talc and blueschist shear zone

20° 16.7537'

164° 25.3542'

Mélange/shear zone (striking 321°)

→ meter-sized blocks in talc + phyllosilicate matrix

→ some fuchsite around possibly

NC18-14

A1: "unzoned" blueschist from rock w/ garnet veins

B: metasilt - metabasite contact

C: metabasite alteration contact

D: alteration next to B, C

E: dark green alteration

A2: glaucophanite w/ fuchsite (?) rim

F: float coarse-grained, garnet, mica

Stop 11

20° 17.1297'

164° 24.9961'

- more mélange just up the road
- Christian has a sample here NC-17 HP 05
- what P-T were these shear zones active?

Stop 12

Blueschist block in mélange w/ talc, chl. rns

06/13/18 Day 4

Spudler et al. 2008 papers

→ TCO1 site

• quarried serp-talc-chl. zone

20° 17.7328'

164° 25.4790'

• tiny ngt. in the rock

• found reaction block

NC18-15

A - glaucophane, chl. core

B - actinolite (?) rxn.

C - dead serp.

D - chl. talc serp. schist

• first example of Zoned we went to... crossite

NC18-16

A - gt. w/o clino. veins

B - gt. w/ clino. veins

→ on the way to the serp outcrop

20° 17.8931'

164° 25.7769'

→ block in blk metabas. ; Fe-rich layers (cm-scale)
multi-meter also aroundNC18-17

→ blocks on side of road

→ gt., qtz., dark-green mineral, qtz-garnet pods

→ on hill w/ large blocks

20° 17.9093'

164° 25.7952'

Spindler 3010 site

Harzburgite, highly weathered - reminds me of MMS.F
 du Sud
 could not get a sample
 some metabasite at edge
 several hundred meters wide

End of road

20° 18.0941'

164° 26.1750'

Metabasite, similar to NC18-16
 blocks

clinzoisite, gt., glauc., gts. are zoned

After lunch

Road walk/drive up NE coast of Pam Peninsula

20° 14.4577'

164° 20.2542'

NC18-18 x 3 samples

→ gt w/ incl.-rich core and diff (lighter) rim

→ clinzoisite veins

→ quarry up road

NC18-19

→ qtz vein sample (not as fresh) in float

20° 14.5237'

164° 20.2451'

NC18-20 A, B

A - greener sample

B - ^{qtz.} sample with veins

→ these samples are greener than the last two stops

20° 14.6296'

164° 20.2438'

NC18-21

20° 15.0292'

164° 20.1432'

→ meta-tuff in stream w/ small garnet stringers, qtz, amphi.

→ on approach to m. (sp?) hill in middle of transect

NC18-22

chl.-talc schist in multi-meter road atcrop

20° 15.1413'

164° 20.1816'

NC18-23

clinzoisite veins in metabasite

near serp. pod

20° 15.1879'

164° 20.1058'

just up road (~20 m) layered eclogite

w/ qtz -qt. layers

Notes for last day

Check the quarry sample (NC18-04)

06/14/18 Day 5

20° 20.4135'

164° 25.4192'

NC18-24 SKETCHY

ep.-genc., no garnet

walking behind Total gas station

All metasediment outcrops, metabasite road outcrops everywhere (some of it large); probably not from here, but taking a sample in case

collecting a sample (unusual) w/ cross-cutting veins - this one is gtz? and otherwise one is phg. + something else... it has a rim

20° 21.0622'

164° 26.0430'

NC18-25

→ zone 1, sample from backyard

Col de Parais

NC18-26

A - lawsonite?

B - serpentinite sample

(- maybe less weathered
lawsonite sample)

20° 20.5210'

164° 26.4327'

outcrop on Col de Parais road, just up from Dispensaire; mafic-ultramafic contact

NC18-27

A - block nearest road; more massive

B - chl.-bearing reaction metabasite

20° 20.4821'

164° 26.4555'

These blocks are quite heterogeneous -
where are they coming from?

looking across at other road (not on Pam-avega)
that might sample northern portion of ^{map} PEM
stringer

NC18-28

fresh, massive metabasite, green colored from black

20° 20.4215'

164° 26.5305'

NC18-29

20° 20.4094'

164° 26.5575'

A - Massive green fine-grained w/ep. + qtz.

B - Contact b/t massive and coarse-grained

C - foliated rim (?) deformed around pod?
chlorite, some qtz, nice glauc. needles

20° 20.2533'

164° 26.7415'

View relating boulder field and the school outcrops
from the first day (NC18-02)

the hill that the boulders are on is probably
all metabasite

NC18-30

→ in the other Diabot stringer (past the outcrops)

→ Fine-grained glauc-rich sample in boulder
tumbling from top of hill

20° 19.83~~12~~164° 26.96~~35~~

A - fine-grained glauc.

B - gt. - bearing from top of slope.

NC18-31

A - blueschist

B - talc - chl

outcrop zone on Col de Parais road

relation zone

20° 20.4483'

164° 26.4485'

NC18-32

Amoss Beach

- A - clinozoisite vein feature at green beach zone
- B - vein (qtz, phg.) below qtz boudin
- C - swirly qtz rich sample
- D - ~~the~~ distinct colors
- E - glaucophane from down beach

End of sample collection before driving to
Noumea

NC18-33

Poyu built @ excursion stop

Questions for Pierre and Bernard

- details of how the map was made (Combo. of remote sensing and mapping?)
- interested in fluid-related features - veining, bleach zones, small-scale ^{variable} retrogression - how common
- studying oxidation state of exhumed subducted complexes
- shear zones - mylonite zone near Yanbé
- maps distinct shear zones vs. big shear zone?
- serpentinite - where is it found, relation to Massif du Sud

Aberge de Jennesse de Poé

21° 36' 36.05" S

165° 23' 28.75" E

Poya

21° 40' 37.8" S

165° 32' 56.1" E

- Sample more outcrops of Poya basalt
- Sample here - sep outcrop from Fitherbart of 01, 2004
- beach walk near eclogite veins
- finish traverse in NW portion of island
- jungle traverse SE of that
- Avada Stream; Amoss Creek
- rest of Amoss coastline
- metabasite @ Col de Amoss
- road spotted on just day

06/18/2018

Headed out with Stéphane Lesimple to

Sample west coast Poya basalt and some Kone
facies, then to east to go to Fitzherbert outcrop
and some blueschist SE of there

NC18-34

→ Poya basalt (?) road outcrop

22° 7.9997'

164° 20.3699'

- relatively coarse-grained; plagioclase visible
- fine white veins in some areas
- also red argillite clays (bedded) - they
are associated with Poya basalts and not Kone facies
- two sets of veins - large, late one w/ coarse calcite,
thinner ones that are ambiguous

NC18-35

21° 29.2290'

165° 24.8270'

→ finer-grained basalt, maybe slightly less fresh than
NC18-34

→ perhaps more evidence here in the clay veins for ocean
floor alteration

NC18-36

21° 2.7160'

164° 52.6327'

- large basalt quarry part Kone
- Kone facies - still overlying sediment
- sampled from caterpillar digger

→ Ender borehole, fresh basalt
Tectonophyses

→ mag. Schwartz; Pear's and somewhere else

Voh pillows (see app for GPS)
 → too weathered to sample

NC18-37

21° 0.7548'

164° 52.0404

- Poya basalt outcrop in stream bed - also
 Stéphane found red jasper rock which means
 Poya, not koni (black argillite)
 → still fine-grained, no sign of white veins
 @ outcrop scale

06/19/2018

drove from [redacted] house across
to east side and up past Highline to
Fitzherbert exp outcrop

(NC18-38)

→ blueschist blocks on slope below Fitzherbert site

20° 27.2684'

164° 39.5911'

A - finer, fresher

B - slightly less fresh with clinopyroxene
veins, retrogressed garnets, coarser gr.
grain size

- road dead-ends @ a waterfall control thing

(NC18-39) !!!

→ fresh hornf. w/ exp. rind (i.e. veins), sulfide? (blk shiny)

20° 27.4586'

164° 39.2935'

→ also a sample from hornf. w/ pyroxene banding
(like south) (B)

→ also a random one from near A (C)

06/20/18

20° 39.2166'

164° 53.2372'

large metabasalt block

→ looks more retrogressed - epidote, greenschist

NC18-40

A - from big block; some epidote

B - more siliceous block, greenschist facies?

Beach walk (parked @ Exxon)

NC18-41

→ on beach walk, immediately, you see retrogressed green meta-basalts w/ late qtz veins

→ progressively gets more blue

→ found a metabasalt block in contact w/ metaseds + talc zone

A - metabasalt (unaltered)

B - talc/chl. zone

C - smaller meta-basalt block (see photo)

NC18-42

20° 39.7829'

164° 55.7981'

metabasalt w/ clinzoisite veins (very much like the north)
block

A →

B - contact @ edge of block

NC18-43

20° 39.3797'

164° 55.4810'

weathered serp. outcrop @ water's edge

→ MANY veins; for thin section only

NC18-44

→ large river below bridge at camp

→ fine-grained green meta-dolerite

20° 45.7547'

165° 6.7750'

→ Cluzel described this about kani facies, blue amphibole visible here

NC18-45

Road back to the west coast

20° 54.4225'

165° 6.6706'

→ in Boghen terrane

→ massive serp. (mostly K-feldspar)

· metamorphosed (greenschist) seds so therefore

the serp might also be metamorphosed

· ~~seds~~ seds as lenses and blocks (but volumetrically small)

NC18-46

20° 56.7105'

165° 2.1835'

→ more sep. in Bagher; another meta-sed lens

NC18-47

21° 32.4464'

165° 59.8694'

→ Poya block, more fractures (small)

→ red argillite present

NC18-49

→ sep. @ metamorphic sole

21° 34.0386'

166° 5.0640'

NC18-48

21° 28.5022'

165° 47.7875'

→ Doyu basalt; what is the vein? late or hydrothermal?

→ looking at Qwawa (sp?) mine

